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TUBERCULOSIS: EPIDEMIOLOGY ASPECTS AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES IN UKRAINE (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Abstract.

Tuberculosis (TB) remains a serious public health problem in Ukraine, which requires a systemic approach to prevention and treatment. The article provides an analysis of the epidemiological situation, considered risk factors for the spread of the disease, and proposed strategies for its prevention.

Key words: tuberculosis, risk factors, morbidity, mortality, preventive measures

Introduction

Tuberculosis is an infectious disease caused by mycobacteria of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex. The main route of transmission is airborne, which makes the disease especially dangerous in conditions of high social mobility and densely populated areas.

Tuberculosis (TB) is a preventable and usually curable disease. However, in 2023, tuberculosis is likely to return to the status of the world's leading cause of death from an infectious agent, after 3 years in which it was replaced by the coronavirus (COVID-19), and caused almost twice as many deaths as HIV/AIDS. More than 10 million people continue to suffer from tuberculosis each year, and the number is increasing from 2021.

The analysis of the epidemiological situation showed that, according to current epidemiological surveillance, in 2023 the incidence of TB was 48.4 per 100 thousand population (new cases and relapses) and increased by 7.3% compared to 2022 (45.1 per 100 thousand . population).

The influence of military actions on the population's access to medical services is clearly visible, which is reflected in the morbidity data in those regions of Ukraine in which there is a temporary occupation of part of the territories. [1]

Analysis of morbidity and mortality rates in Ukraine showed that the country remains one of the European countries with a high level of TB prevalence. In 2023, more than 3,600 deaths from this disease were recorded.

The share of children under 14 among new cases is 639, which indicates the need to strengthen vaccination.

Risk factors[2]:

- Socio-economic conditions: poverty, malnutrition, cramped living conditions.
- Associated diseases: HIV infection, diabetes, addiction to psychoactive substances.

- Problems in the health care system: insufficient vaccination coverage and limited access to diagnostics

Preventive measures, in particular vaccination, are important. Introduction of BCG. To protect children's

bodies from the development of severe generalized forms of TB, such as tuberculous meningitis and miliary TB, which can lead to fatal cases, mass immunization of newborns with the BCG vaccine is carried out. [1]

Screening and early diagnosis: the use of modern methods, such as molecular diagnostics, allows the detection of TB in the early stages. Access to fluoroscopy needs to be increased, especially in remote areas [3] Today, the WHO identifies two priority risk groups that should be prioritized when organizing systematic targeted screening [4,5]:

1. People with an increased risk of progression from infection to active TB:

- HIV-infected persons;
- patients with silicosis;
- patients starting or planning treatment with tumor necrosis factor inhibitors;
- patients receiving dialysis;
- patients who are preparing for organ transplantation or hematological transfusions.

2. Patients with an increased risk of TB disease:

- focal contacts of people with bacteriologically confirmed TB, which are usually divided into:

1) children under the age of five; 2) children over the age of five, teenagers and adults;

- prisoners, health care workers, immigrants from countries with a high burden of TB, the homeless, and people who use drugs

According to WHO estimates, about 20–24% of TB cases are underdiagnosed in Ukraine every year, and the negative impact caused by Russia's military aggression against Ukraine has exacerbated the crisis of underdiagnosis of TB in Ukraine, which indicates the need for a more active approach to early TB detection and explains the need for systematic screening of persons at defined risk groups for the development of TB.[1]

Conclusions.

Tuberculosis in Ukraine remains an epidemiological challenge, exacerbated by socio-economic and medical problems.

An effective fight against TB is possible only under the condition of comprehensive prevention, which includes vaccination, screening, treatment and social support.

Future research should be aimed at improving methods of diagnosis and therapy, as well as at monitoring resistant strains. Solving the TB problem in Ukraine requires a multifaceted approach. Integration of medical, social and educational measures is necessary. Special emphasis should be placed on the fight against antimicrobial resistance, which is a serious obstacle to effective treat

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